

KEY FACTORS IN REDUCING COST OF UAM IMPLEMENTATION

Abstract

Purpose – identification of the main factors affecting the cost of UAM based on results of ASSURED-UAM project. These factors can be found among such cost areas as: investments (infrastructure, aircraft), operational, energy, end of life, delay, environmental. Once determined, they be of great value for all UAM stakeholders, including manufacturers, urban planners, air service providers.

Design/methodology/approach – the obtained results were based on the outcomes of ASSURED-UAM project. Having the information about the magnitude of each cost category, we were able to identify the most costly factors of UAM. As a result, it was possible to suggest feasible cost reduction means.

Findings – for each cost category there is the possibility to lower its value amongst the total cost of UAM. Each cost category has its own cost reduction means. It is vital however that the obtained results depend strongly on the assumptions made at the beginning of cost calculations.

Keywords – UAM, ELCC, Life cycle analysis, UAV, Drones, Sustainability

Paper type – Technical paper

Introduction

UAM (Urban Air Mobility) encompasses aerial means of transportation, both cargo and personal, utilizing modern technologies to help reduce ground traffic congestions and optimise public services in cities. [According to the EU Regulations 2019/947 and 2019/945, drones flights are encompassed within three categories: open, specific and certified. All categories differ in the risk level of the operation.](#) Although the UAM is believed to offer extraordinary experiences, at the same time it delivers doubts concerning the economic aspects and profitability.

Therefore, for the sake of the public awareness and also for all UAM stakeholders, cost of unmanned aviation should be assessed and exposed to various comparisons with other means of transportation.

There are many approaches to the calculation of the total life cycle costing based on LCAs (life cycle assessment). One of them is ELCC.

Environmental life-cycle costing (ELCC) analysis allows to calculate the total cost of the product including environmental aspects (ISO, 2006) (Swarr, et al., 2011) (Gompf, et al., 2020). Due to the fact that urban air mobility encompasses a wide spectrum of products and services, the comprehensive analysis like ELCC is the most suitable tool.

The results of the ELCC may deliver clear indications about UAM cost reduction means which fits in scope of flagship actions given in the Drone Strategy 2.0 published by European Commission in 2022. As the overall goal of future UAM is to be cost effective in terms of introduction of unmanned flights and integrating them within common airspace with general aviation, key factors for UAM cost efficiency should be identified.

Environmental life-cycle costing of UAM

Due to the fact that UAM systems and the dedicated aircraft are in infant phase of development, part of our input originates from a long history of classic aircraft, especially data covering operational aspects of flight. For the purpose of comparing transport modes in terms of energy efficiency, we adopted unitary data and the method from a 2017 EC DG MOVE's report on urban accessibility (Biedka, et al., 2017).

Method

Life cycling costing is an additional analysis to the well know LCA (life cycle assessment) that delivers direct information about the costs at each phase of the product's lifetime. The term environmental LCC means that the analysis covers the costs related to the product or service impact on environment.

Environmental life-cycle costing (ELCC) analysis consists of the following components:

$$ELCC = C_{ic} + C_e + C_o + C_s + C_{env} + C_d \quad (1)$$

where:

C_{ic} investment costs

C_e energy costs

C_o operating costs

C_s delay and deadhead costs

C_{env} environmental costs

C_d end of life costs

Investment costs involve the costs of product (aircraft) purchase, cost of construction works (landing pad/vertiport), necessary equipment installation, and many more. In principle, these costs are born at the very beginning of the investment process and typically have the biggest contribution to the total cost. Energy costs relates to the feeding of propulsion system of the aircraft (Stolaroff, et al., 2018) (Zhang, et al., 2021) (Bacchini & Cestino, 2019) while the second one refers to the energy consumed by the airport/vertiport (Li, et al., 2017) (Ortega Alba & Manana, 2017) (Costa, et al., 2012). Operating costs (direct and indirect) are all costs born during the operational phase of the UAM services. Delay cost (Liu, et al., 2019) (Alvear Cardenas, et al., 2017) (Cook & Tanner, 2015) is a compensation that airline must pay to its customer due to flight delay. Deadhead costs (Uber Elevate, 2016) are costs of non-revenue flights e.g. UAS repositioning flights.

Environmental costs reflect the EU strategy and policy (DG Climate Action European Commission, 2021) (EC, 2003) and include emissions costs reflected as CO2 equivalent, where the emissions associated to electric UAVs are the internalized emission costs depending on local differences in electricity mix (Cerdas, et al., 2018) – and – noise pollution (EC, 1996) (EC, 2002). Finally, end of life costs internalize recycling, incineration or landfilling costs of a product that reached its life end (Hao, et al., 2017) (Yoder, 2017) (Pham & Yun, 2018) (Zeng, et al., 2018) (Meng, et al., 2018) (Cousins, et al., 2019) (Soo, et al., 2019).

UAM use cases

We calculated ELLC costs for the ASSURED use cases (ASSURED-UAM D1.4, 2021) for three time horizons - 2025, 2030 and 2035, three countries – Italy, Poland and Portugal, assumed vehicles performances (ASSURED-UAM D1.1, 2021), and regulatory constraints (ASSURED-UAM D1.2, 2021). **Counties were selected on the basis of the project scope that assumed research initiatives connected with those areas.** Among the use cases are those related to the small and big cargo operations as well as personal aerial transportation systems. In order to compare the costs in different countries, three European countries were chosen. Costs calculations for operations in all use cases include the return flight from the destination points. See Table 1

Table 1 UAM Use cases description for ELCC analysis.

Use case description	Use Case mission definition
UC 2025 1 Direct last-mile delivery	Commercially driven simple operations of local delivery of small, light parcels from defined distribution point to final destinations including delivery of goods.
UC 2025 2 Point-to-point public services	Point-to-point operations executing high-priority public service related tasks like medical transport of blood, medicines, medical samples or other light load.
UC 2030 3 Advanced last mile delivery	Commercially driven operations of local delivery of more than one small, light parcel during single mission from defined distribution point to individual receivers and automatic parcel lockers.
UC 2030 4 Point-to-everywhere public services	Point-to-everywhere operations executing high-priority public service related tasks as in the case of UC2 but more complex and demanding like medical transport of first-aid equipment blood, blood for donation, blood samples, human plasma, laboratory samples, etc
UC 2035 5 Direct medical transport of people	Short, direct test operations of unmanned medical transport of passengers/patients between hospitals initially supervised by human operator within single metropolitan area.

UC 2035 | 6
Automatic personal aerial transportation

Personal transport of people over densely populated areas, assisted by pilot onboard, optionally in automatic flight mode as an initial phase to fully autonomous flights.

The use cases reflect the initial phase of UAM service deployment (i.a. in terms of number of operations). Expectations on further UAM system development follow the trajectory (ASSURED-UAM D2.5, 2022) (ASSURED-UAM D2.6, 2022). In Table 2, below, please consider the main quantitative assumptions of the use cases.

Table 2 UAM Use cases description for ELCC analysis - inputs.

Use case description	UAS configuration	Number of aircraft	Number of landing pads/vertiports	Vehicle Gross Weight [kg]	Payload [kg]	Flight Range [km]
UC 2025 1 Direct last-mile delivery	Multicopter VTOL	40	20	25	5	20
UC 2025 2 Point-to-point public services	Multicopter VTOL	50	25	25	5	30
UC 2030 3 Advanced last mile delivery	Decoupled propulsion VTOL	5	8	1 000	150	50
UC 2030 4 Point-to-everywhere public services	Decoupled propulsion VTOL	8	12	235	35	80
UC 2035 5 Direct medical transport of people	Decoupled propulsion VTOL	5	12	1 000	150	200
UC 2035 6 Automatic personal aerial transportation	Decoupled propulsion VTOL	4	6	2 400	360	80

For more information, especially quantitative details, please refer to the ASSURED-UAM report on ELCC estimation (ASSURED-UAM D2.3, 2021). *As this paper focuses mainly on the analysis of obtained ELCC outcomes, detailed calculations were not presented in order to maintain clarity of the analysis on costs reduction means.*

Results

Obtained ELCC results are given for three countries: Poland, Italy and Portugal because the goal was to identify the UAM costs in countries with different industry development level and energy infrastructure available. In order to compare the

operations within given six use cases, calculated costs are expressed in the same unit, either EUR/kg km or EUR/pax km, meaning that the given values show the cost of transportation of 1 kg per 1 km or 1 passenger per 1 km, whether it's cargo drone or passenger aircraft.

Among those nations in terms of the ELCC, Portugal is the one with the highest total cost of all UAM operations, whereas the lowest total costs can be found in Poland. Investment costs constitute the most significant share of the ELLC. Small cargo drones and passenger aircraft have much higher total unit costs in terms of kg-km or passenger-km. See Figure 1.

Figure 1 ELCC analysis results for Poland, Italy, Portugal.

Results details in Poland

In order to show detailed breakdown structure of ELCC for a chosen country, in Table 3, we present the results of the ELLC for Poland. The negligible importance of the environmental costs, as assessed in our analysis, does not reflect actual importance of effort to find more sustainable mobility solutions, generating less emissions, less noise and less waste.

Table 3 ELCC analysis details for Poland.

	2025		2030		2035	
	UC 1	UC 2	UC 3	UC 4	UC 5	UC 6
Energy costs [EUR/year]	304	304	10 186	3160	15 344	18 570

Operational costs [EUR/year]	471 360	503 610	883 360	556 360	796 360	1 234 360
Delay costs [EUR/year]	1500	1500	45 000	10 500	0	845
Environmental costs [EUR/year]	1321	1380	6692	2827	6661	7987
End of life costs [EUR/year]	128	161	509	186	294	564
Total costs [EUR/year]	474 613	506 955	945 747	573 033	818 659	1 262 326
Investment costs [EUR]	3 600 000	4 500 000	7 100 000	4 400 000	6 300 000	8 400 00

Energy costs

Amongst low value costs are also those related to energy consumption. It is expected that aircraft or infrastructure energy consumption will be low because of the fact that there won't be many drones operating within urban area in the nearest future, translating to low energy costs in total. As we can see in Figure 2, energy costs are mainly driven by aircraft energy consumption. Moreover, the bigger the aircraft (as in Use case 3 and 6), the higher its share of energy costs. Illustration of the energy costs breakdown structure is given below.

Figure 2 Energy costs breakdown structure in Poland.

Operational costs

Figure 3 allows to identify further differences among the mobility services because of substantiations in operational costs for described use cases. Cost of flight and administrative expenses are, relatively, much higher for small delivery drones services (Use case 1) in comparison to passenger UAM services (Use case 6). Cost of fees associated to non-operational time are irrelevant in case of Use case 1 and, similarly important, for other cases. Also, because passenger services include much more expensive equipment, depreciation costs are very significant.

Figure 3 Operational costs breakdown structure for Poland.

Delay costs

Delay costs don't stand out among the others as no serious delays are not expected to occur in the early stage of UAM adoption. Perhaps, with an intensification of drones traffic in the air, the delays will grow in number and duration.

Environmental costs

UAM impact on environment focuses mainly on two aspects: gas pollution and noise pollution. Noise pollution cost is nearly negligible for small delivery drones services and becomes more important for passenger UAM services (larger UAS). This is due to the fact that larger drones possess in general more or bigger propellers which generate substantial amount of noise. On the other hand, more prominent is the cost of CO2 and other greenhouse gases pollution. This is due to the fact that European Commission imposes increasing fares for gases emissions. Although given use cases describe operations with electric drones, the source of energy for aircraft or ground infrastructure maintenance is based mostly on fossil fuels at the moment. Of course the contribution of fossil fuels and renewable energy differs depending on the country and thus the environmental costs and is prone to change in the future.

Figure 4 Environmental costs breakdown structure.

End of life costs

End of life costs which are related mainly to the recycling processes, which have a positive impact on the manufacturing costs as they deliver materials to build cheaper vehicles and buildings. Worth mentioning is that the recycling of materials or structures of drones are relatively at low level at the moment, however it is predicted that with an advancement of recycling processes, more benefits will be delivered leading to decreased manufacturing or recycling costs.

Investment costs

As for the investment costs, landing infrastructure for passenger operations is equally costly as aircraft itself but in case of operations with smaller cargo drones, landing infrastructure becomes more dominant in terms of total investment costs. This is due to the fact that small drones manufacturing is relatively low compared to the costs of building the landing pads on ground. See Figure 4.

Figure 4 Investment costs breakdown structure.

Conclusions

The UAM deployment should be, especially in passenger transport, concerned with the initial investment costs. High standards require extra careful considerations on where and what to develop. In case of wrong decisions at the beginning, the system would need to be constantly supported from the outside (risk of sunk costs) and may offer inadequate services hard to adjust (e.g. unused vertiports, inadequate capacity of aircraft). For a full list of identified factors see Table 4.

Table 4 Identification of key factors in reducing the total cost of implementation of Urban Air Mobility.

Cost category	Cost name	Cost reduction means
Energy	Energy consumption	Improved energy effectiveness of ground infrastructure and aircraft
	Justification: In order to decrease the energy costs, more effective aircraft and ground infrastructure must be developed. This means that UAV propulsion and ground infrastructure operation must be less energy consumptive at the same working conditions as it is today.	
	Depreciation	Decreased investment costs
	Justification: As the depreciation cost is a derivative of initial investment cost of aircraft or ground infrastructure, the lesser the investment cost, the lesser the depreciation value.	
	Passenger services	Automation of manual services
	Justification: Passenger services are managed by a team of specialists. Limiting the number of staff by introducing the automated operations might contribute to lowering the passenger services costs.	
Operational	Flight services (pilots, dispatchers)	Development of UAS operations' autonomy
	Justification: Pilots and dispatchers in UAM affect high flight costs. Shifting towards more automated flights, firstly semi- and then fully automated, meaning unmanned, might reduce the flight services costs.	
	Administrative expenses	Improved administrative services
	Justification: Pilots and dispatchers in UAM affect high flight costs. Shifting towards more automated flights, firstly semi- and then fully automated, meaning unmanned, might reduce the flight services costs.	
Delay	Delay duration	Improved traffic management systems
	Justification: Many flights in general aviation are delayed due weather conditions or operational constraints. Developing the systems that will allow for the most optimal management of UAVs during unexpected events might reduce the delays and thus additional costs.	
Environmental	Noise and carbon emissions	Renewable energy driven aircraft Aircraft configurations with silent rotors
	Justification: Environment is affected by transportation both by pollutants and noise generated. Shifting towards the renewable energy sources might reduce substantially carbon footprint while more efficient and optimized rotors might lower the noise of UAVs.	
End of life	Recycling	New and improved recycling technologies
	Justification: Nowadays new manufacturing technologies are available to produce robust and lightweight structures as well as functional devices. Lack of effective means of recycling used components contributes to carbon footprint and lack of materials recycling and reuse. New recycling technologies might enable reuse of materials from used components making manufacturing costs lower.	
Investment	Ground infrastructure construction Aircraft acquisition	Increased (mass) production of structural components Increased demand for UAM operations
	Justification: Because of single production of UAVs' prototypes, the manufacturing costs are very high. Increasing the number of aircraft dedicated to UAM might decrease their unit costs. Same applies to ground infrastructure.	

Identified key factors for UAM costs reduction suggest that increased automation and autonomy of the UAS may affect the decrease of both initial and operational cost. Fully automated and unmanned passenger services at vertiports supported with novel multimodal travel systems should minimise time and money spent on the trip before boarding the aircraft. What is more, development of novel propulsion and energy storage technologies such as hydrogen fuel cells, new generation of batteries is crucial in achieving energy and flight range goals of future aviation and thus leading to the reduction of energy costs. On the other hand, shifting from manned to unmanned flights which may reduce costs substantially raises risks of safety. Therefore, to maintain sufficient safety levels, UAV manufacturers should develop and implement new solutions in terms of geo awareness. One of them is DAA (detect and avoid) which can be conducted by e.g. optical sensing or satellite positioning (ads-b). Furthermore, communication between manned and unmanned aviation should be conducted via low latency and robust technologies, both cellular (5g, 6g) and satellite (ads-b). As increased number of aircraft operating in urban and suburban areas have impact on environment, UAS manufacturers should consider additional costs related to this matter. Thereby, improvement in the design of propellers combined with greener power generation means should lead to cleaner and quieter urban air mobility. These issues are the subject of working groups set up by JARUS, ICAO or EASA. Outcomes of their work, especially on aircraft design, vertiports, automation, safety, environment combined with our costs results may cast a light on the most important issues leading to efficient UAM implementation.

Further Work

The results of ELCC analysis are as realistic as the input data utilized in the calculations. As UAM is at the beginning of its development and implementation into cities, the real data from the industry is of great value for conducting reliable economic and engineering analysis. Therefore, it is recommended to follow the UAM market and gather data and parameters from UAM companies and actors to use them in the ELCC analysis for a more precise recalculation.

Another aspect for future work is the impact of energy generation means on the UAM industry. As the new aircraft configurations rely mostly on electric energy, and the fact that electricity mix differs depending on the country, the electricity mix change and therefore deviations in the cost of energy should be monitored and included in the recalculated ELCC.

In order to address the issues presented in the Drone Strategy 2.0, new technologies leading to the cost effective and safe integration of UAM and general aviation should be developed.

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References

- Alvear Cardenas, J. I. i inni, 2017. Aircraft Departure Delay and its Associated Costs for Airlines and Airports in Europe.
- ASSURED-UAM D1.1, 2021. *D1.1 Technology readiness review*. (no place): H2020-MG-2020-SingleStage-INEA.
- ASSURED-UAM D1.2, 2021. *D1.2 Regulatory Framework*. (no place): H2020-MG-2020-SingleStage-INEA.
- ASSURED-UAM D1.4, 2021. *D1.4 Initial ConOps Definition*. (no place): H2020-MG-2020-SingleStage-INEA.
- ASSURED-UAM D2.3, 2021. *D2.3 UAM ELCC+E estimation*. (no place): H2020-MG-2020-SingleStage-INEA.
- ASSURED-UAM D2.5, 2022. D2.5 Opening scenarios for UAM in future integrated urban mobility system. (no place): H2020-MG-2020-SingleStage-INEA.
- ASSURED-UAM D2.6, 2022. D2.6 Final scenarios for UAM in future integrated urban mobility system. (no place): H2020-MG-2020-SingleStage-INEA.
- Bacchini, A. i Cestino, E., 2019. Electric VTOL Configurations Comparison. *MDPI aerospace*.
- Biedka, M., Hitchcock, G., Fiorello, D. i Fermi, F., 2017. Study on urban mobility – Assessing and improving the accessibility of urban areas: Annexe 3: Task 3 Report – Relative efficiency of urban passenger transport modes, Brussels: European Commission DG MOVE.
- Cerdas, F., Egede, P. i Herrmann, C., 2018. LCA of Electromobility. W: *Life Cycle Assessment: Theory and Practice*. (no place): Springer International Publishing AG, pp. 669-693.
- Cook, A. J. i Tanner, G., 2015. *European airline delay cost reference values*, Brussels: EUROCONTROL Performance Review Unit.
- Costa, A., Blanes, L. M., Donnelly, C. i Keane, M. M., 2012. Review of EU airport energy interests and priorities with respect to ICT, energy efficiency and enhanced building operation. Manchester, CASCADE - ICT for Energy Efficient Airports.
- Cousins, D. S. i inni, 2019. Recycling glass fiber thermoplastic composites from wind turbine blades. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Tom 209.
- DG Climate Action European Commission, 2021. *2050 long-term strategy*. [Online]
Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/2050-long-term-strategy_en
[Data uzyskania dostępu: 25 Nov 2021].
- EC, 1996. COMMISSION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITIES FUTURE NOISE POLICY - European Commission Green Paper COM/96/0540 FINAL. (no place): (no name).
- EC, 2002. Directive 2002/49/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 June 2002 relating to the assessment and management of environmental noise - Declaration by the Commission in the Conciliation Committee on the Directive relating to the assessment a. (no place): (no name).

EC, 2003. DIRECTIVE 2003/87/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 13 October 2003 establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC. (no place): (no name).

Gompf, K., Traverso, M. i Hetterich, J., 2020. Towards social life cycle assessment of mobility services: systematic literature review and the way forward. *Int J Life Cycle Assess*, Issue 25, p. 1883–1909.

Hao, H., Qiao, Q., Liu, Z. i Zhao, F., 2017. Impact of recycling on energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions from electric vehicle production: The China 2025 case. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, Tom 122.

ISO, 2006. International standard ISO 14044 environmental management–life cycle assessment–requirements and guidelines. Geneva: ISO.

Li, B. i inni, 2017. Research and Analysis on Energy Consumption Features of Civil Airports. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.*, Tom 94(1):012134.

Liu, Y., Yin, M. i Hansen, M., 2019. Estimating Costs of Flight Delay for Air Cargo Operations. *Transportation Research Part E Logistics and Transportation Review*, Tom 125.

Meng, F., McKechnie, J. & Pickering, S. J., 2018. An assessment of financial viability of recycled carbon fibre in automotive applications. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Volume 109.

Ortega Alba, S. i Manana, M., 2017. Energy Research in Airports: A Review. *Energies*, Tom 9(5).

Pham, T. H. i Yun, S., 2018. Basic Materials Initiating on Titanium Industry; Investors, Prepare for Take-Off, (no place): Jeffries Franchise Note.

Soo, V. K. i inni, 2019. Economic and Environmental Evaluation of Aluminium Recycling. *Procedia Manufacturing*, Tom 33.

Stolaroff, J. K. i inni, 2018. Energy use and life cycle greenhouse gas emissions of drones for commercial package delivery. *Nat Commun*, 9(409).

Swarr, T. E., Hunkeler, D. i Klöpffer, W., 2011. Environmental life-cycle costing: a code of practice. *Int J Life Cycle Assess*, Issue 16, p. 389–391.

Uber Elevate, 2016. Fast-Forwarding to a Future of On-Demand Urban Air Transportation, (no place): Uber, Inc..

Yoder, C., 2017. *Cost to Recycle Metal*. [Online]

Available at: <http://recycleucson.com/cost-recycle-metal/>

[Data uzyskania dostępu: 25 Oct 2021].

Zeng, X., Mathews, J. A. i Li, J., 2018. Urban Mining of E-Waste is Becoming More Cost-Effective Than Virgin Mining. *Environmental Science and Technology*, Tom 52(8).

Zhang, J., Campbell, J. F., Sweeney II, D. C. i Hupman, A. C., 2021. Energy consumption models for delivery drones: A comparison and assessment. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, Tom 90.

Additional Sources

Nomenclature

ASSURED-UAM - Acceptance, Safety and Sustainability Recommendations for Efficient Deployment of UAM, a project of H2020-MG-2020-SingleStage-INEA, 2021-2022

DG MOVE - Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport of the European Commission

EC - European Commission

ELCC - Environmental life-cycle costing

LCA - Life Cycle Assessment

UAM - Urban Air Mobility

UAS - Unmanned Aerial System

UAV - Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

UC - use case